

DIELECTRIC CONSTANT AND DIPOLE MOMENT : PYRIDINE AND 2:4:6-TRIMETHYLPYRIDINE

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The dielectric constants and densities of pyridine and 2:4:6-trimethylpyridine have been measured in pure liquid state over a range of temperature. The dielectric constant and density of pyridine in solution have been measured at various concentrations. The moments are calculated by applying the D.C.M., the Onsager, the Kirkwood and the new equations.

In the present work, the dielectric constant and density of pyridine in pure liquid state have been measured over a range of temperature. Measurements have also been made for solutions of pyridine in benzene. The moments have been calculated by the new, the Onsager and the Kirkwood equations.

The moment of pyridine was determined by a number of workers (Table I).

TABLE I

Author	Solvent.	μ_D .	μ_{Ons} .
Lange ¹	Benzene	2.11	
Bergmann ²	"	2.21	
Böttcher ³	Liquid, 25-114°	...	2.25-2.37
Leis and Curran ⁴	Benzene	2.20	
	Dioxane	2.22	
Middleton and Partington ⁵	Hexane	2.21	
	cycloHexane	2.20	
	CCl ₄	2.33	
	Benzene	2.26	
	Toluene	2.25	
	CS ₂	2.10	

1. Lange, *Z. Physik*, 1926, 33, 169.
2. Bergmann, *Ber.*, 1922, 55, 446.
3. Böttcher, *Physica*, 1939, 6, 59.
4. Leis and Curran, *J. Amer Chem Soc.*, 1945, 67, 79.
5. Middleton and Partington, *Nature*, 1938, 141, 516.

The moment of 2:4:6-trimethylpyridine in benzene solution was determined by Govinda Rau and Narayanswamy (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1934, 320, 23) as 1.93. In the present work, the dielectric constants and densities of 2:4:6-trimethylpyridine in pure liquid at various temperatures have been measured for the first time. The moments have been calculated by the application of the Onsager, the Kirkwood and the new equations.

EXPERIMENTAL

Pyridine and 2:4:6-trimethylpyridine were purified by distilling under reduced pressure; pyridine, b. p. 115° (lit. 115°) and 2:4:6-trimethylpyridine, b. p. 170.1 (lit. 170.4°).

TABLE II*

Pyridine.					(b). Pure liquid (Böttcher, <i>loc. cit.</i>).			
(a). Pure liquid.		$P_1 = 102.8.$			Temp.	$\epsilon.$	$d.$	$\mu_{\text{new.}}$
Temp.	$\epsilon.$	$d.$	$P.$	$\mu_{\text{new.}}$				
25°	13.51	0.9788	1011.0	2.22	20°	13.3	0.981	2.17
35°	13.04	0.9677	984.2	2.23	25°	13.3	0.977	2.19
45°	12.57	0.9566	956.6	2.23	50°	11.4	0.953	2.11
55°	12.66	0.9455	933.7	2.23	80°	10.6	0.924	2.15
65°	11.76	0.9344	910.9	2.23	114°	9.5	0.884	2.15
75°	11.35	0.9233	886.7	2.23				
85°	10.96	0.9122	863.8	2.23				

*Present work.

TABLE III

Solvent : benzene (present work).

Temp.	$\epsilon_{12}.$	$d_{12}.$	$P_2.$	$\mu_{\text{new.}}$	$\epsilon_{12}.$	$d_{12}.$	$P_2.$	$\mu_{\text{new.}}$
$\omega_2 = 0.1853$ (or $f_2 = 0.1834$).				$\omega_2 = 0.3717$ (or $f_2 = 0.3687$).				
25°	3.764	0.8942	811.9	1.96	5.547	0.8950	886.3	2.06
30°	3.715	0.8884	798.2	1.96	5.456	0.8891	872.2	2.06
35°	3.667	0.8826	784.3	1.96	5.367	0.8832	857.8	2.06
40°	3.619	0.8768	769.6	1.95	5.272	0.8774	842.0	2.05
45°	3.575	0.8708	758.2	1.95	5.184	0.8714	827.7	2.05
$\omega_2 = 0.5160$ (or $f_2 = 0.5129$).				$\omega_2 = 0.6794$ (or $f_2 = 0.6767$).				
25°	7.218	0.9286	918.5	2.11	9.346	0.9452	973.1	2.18
30°	7.082	0.9230	902.2	2.10	9.181	0.9392	959.8	2.18
35°	6.953	0.9174	886.9	2.10	9.018	0.9332	945.8	2.18
40°	6.816	0.9118	870.2	2.09	8.847	0.9272	930.9	2.18
45°	6.885	0.9062	854.5	2.09	8.688	0.9210	916.4	2.17
$\omega_2 = 0.8351$ (or $f_2 = 0.8333$).								
25°	11.18	0.9616	980.2	2.18				
30°	10.97	0.9564	964.0	2.18				
35°	10.77	0.9512	949.9	2.18				
40°	10.56	0.9460	934.0	2.18				
45°	10.36	0.9408	919.6	2.18				

TABLE IIIA

$f_2.$	$\epsilon_{12}.$	$d_{12}.$	$P_2.$	$\mu_{\text{new.}}$	$f_2.$	$\epsilon_{12}.$	$d_{12}.$	$P_2.$	$\mu_{\text{new.}}$
(a). Solvent : benzene at 12° (Beigman, <i>loc. cit.</i>).					(b). Solvent : benzene at 26° (Kogekar, M.Sc. thesis, Bombay Univ.).				
0.00000	2.2938	0.8844	...	...	0.3085	4.771	0.9007	809.7	1.93
0.01342	2.3931	0.8855	757.8	1.84	0.4434	5.945	0.9229	806.7	1.93
0.01818	2.4275	0.8859	754.6	1.83	0.6950	9.440	0.9437	963.2	2.15
0.04232	2.6083	0.8877	758.7	1.84	0.8543	12.225	0.9579	1063.2	2.20
0.05308	2.6901	0.8886	761.4	1.84	1.0000	13.300	0.9770	...	2.20
(c). Solvent : benzene at 25° (Leis and Curran, <i>loc. cit.</i>).					(d). Solvent : dioxane at 25° (Leis and Curran, <i>loc. cit.</i>).				
0.00000	2.272	0.8731	...	...	0.00000	2.212	1.0281	...	...
0.01108	2.349	0.8742	713.1	1.82	0.01023	2.287	1.0279	733.1	1.85
0.01615	2.385	0.8749	724.4	1.84	0.01605	2.318	1.0275	660.4	1.74
0.02765	2.462	0.8760	712.5	1.82	0.02540	2.396	1.0273	716.6	1.83

TABLE IV*
2 : 4 : 6-Trimethylpyridine.

Temp.	Pure liquid. $P_1 = 162.7$			
	ϵ .	d .	P .	μ_{new}
25°	7.807	0.9225	894.3	2.00
35°	7.502	0.9112	864.8	1.99
45°	7.193	0.8997	834.3	1.97
55°	6.918	0.8882	807.6	1.96
65°	6.639	0.8767	799.6	1.95
75°	6.360	0.8652	752.1	1.94
85°	6.101	0.8537	724.3	1.92

* Present work.

TABLE V

Moments.

Solvent.	μ_{new}		$\mu_{\text{Ons.}}$	$\mu_{\text{Krk.}}$	$\mu_{\text{calc.}}$	
	1.5kT	1.5kT				
Pyridine.						
Vapour ¹	...	...	2.15	...	...	2.25
Liquid ² , 20-114°	2.15	...	...	2.31	2.36	...
Liquid ³ , 25-85°	2.23	...	...	2.34	2.39	...
Benzene ⁴	1.96-2.18	...	...	...	...	...
Benzene ⁴	(1.84)	2.25	2.21	...	...	...
Benzene ⁵	1.93-2.20	...	...	...	...	...
Benzene ⁶	(1.83)	2.24	2.20	...	...	...
Dioxane ⁶	(1.84)	2.25	2.22	...	...	...
2 : 4 : 6-Trimethylpyridine.						
Liquid ³ , 25-85°	1.96	...	...	2.19	2.26	1.97

1. DeMore *et al.*, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1954, 22, 876.
2. Böttcher, *loc. cit.*
3. Present work.
4. Bergman, *loc. cit.*
5. Kogekar, *loc. cit.*
6. Leis and Curran, *loc. cit.*

DISCUSSION

Pyridine.—The new moment of pyridine in pure liquid state is 2.23, which is independent of temperature. The Onsager and the Kirkwood values are 2.31 and 2.36 respectively. The vapour value is 2.15. The new moment in solution in

benzene and dioxane is 1.84 in very dilute solutions. In highly concentrated solutions in benzene, the apparent moment increases with concentration and reaches a value of 2.18 at $f_2=0.9$. This value compares with the new value in the liquid state and also with the vapour value. It appears that in very dilute solutions in benzene and dioxane, there is increased freedom of rotation whereby $2j+1=2$ ($1kT$) increases to $2j+1=3$ ($1.5kT$), as a result of which the moment is increased to 2.24, which compares with the vapour value of the molecule as well as with the new moment found in the liquid state.

The bond moments are $C=N=2.08$ and $C-N=1.37$. This furnishes a resultant moment of 1.83. The C—H bond at the *para* position to N atom has a moment of 0.42. This adds to the above resultant moment and affords a value of 2.25 for the molecular moment. This compares with the vapour value and the new value for liquid pyridine.

2:4:6-Trimethylpyridine.—The new moment of 2:4:6-trimethylpyridine is 1.96, which is independent of temperature. The Onsager and the Kirkwood values are 2.19 and 2.26 respectively. The moment of 2:4:6-trimethylpyridine in the liquid state has been measured for the first time.

The resultant of the bonds C—N and C=N is 1.83. The CH₃ group at the *para* position to N atom contributes only 0.14 to the molecular moment. The net molecular moment is 1.97, which compares with the new value in the liquid state.